

A STUDY ON WORK STRESS OF FEMALE FACULTY MEMBERS IN COLLEGES IN VILLUPURAM DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Faculty(both government and private colleges)frequently suffer from stress owing among other factors, to the characteristics and physical working conditions typically found in their working place. It is estimated that work stress costs the nations billions of dollars a year in lost outputs, health care expenses and stress related lawsuits (National institute for occupational safety and health-2005).Work stress is a timely and important topic for workers, that is the condition in which some factors or combination of factors interferes with the worker to disrupt her physical, psychological or behavioural effect most affected persons by this problems particularly female who irrespective of the unit(public or private)in which they work frequently suffer from stress. Several studies point out those lecturers, assistant professors, HODs report that they feel stress in their work. Through their dealings with suffering, illness they confront existential issues on a daily basis. They have to cope with stress at work and even in their family lives.

INTRODUCTION

Women in the professoriate are more stressed out than men. That's probably not shocking to female professors (or many of their male colleagues). Academic jobs are oversized and growing larger. The economic realities of academia mean that universities require faculty to teach more courses than ever before, while maintaining active research programs, obtaining significant grants and other sources of funding, and mentoring and advising students. Academic careers pose tripartite demands of research, teaching, and service; at many institutions--perhaps the majority--professors find that campus time is taken up mostly by the latter two, leaving research and writing for evenings and weekends - time that many women need to keep up their homes and raise their families. Regardless of whether they hold a career, women tend to shoulder a greater proportion of domestic work than do men, and they typically balance multiple conflicting roles--professional, mother, house worker, etc. When domestic work is coupled with a busy professional life, the workload can become burdensome, and it increases significantly with each child. Many (especially younger, untenured) women in the academy chronically face a difficult choice: to do the research they must do to keep their jobs and earn tenure or complete essential domestic obligations. Many academic women feel that their career opportunities are limited after having children. Colleagues may assume that they have sold out and are no longer committed to their careers--which may influence tenure, promotion, and other opportunities for advancement (like appointment to chairs, deanships, and high-profile committees). Even women who attempt to circumvent the maternal wall by having children during graduate school often are penalized.

PROBLEMS STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

Within the general area of occupational stress, teaching has been identified as one of the most stressful occupations in many countries. Teaching related stress, commonly termed 'teacher stress' is defined as a teacher's experience of "unpleasant, negative emotions, such as anger, anxiety, tension, frustration, or depression, resulting from some aspect of their work as a teacher. Like other forms of occupational stress, it can have serious implications for the healthy functioning of the individual as well as for the organisation in which the individual serves. At a personal level, teaching related stress can affect a teacher's health, well-being, and performance. From an organisational perspective, it translates to unproductive employee behaviours such as alienation, apathy, and absenteeism. Hence, even after nearly

three decades of research effort, the study of teacher stress, particularly its sources and manifestations, continues to attract widespread interest and attention.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To examine the physiological, psychological and behavioural causes for the stress among respondents.
2. To find out whether socio-economic life is affected due to work stress.
3. To study whether the skills are same for different experienced faculty members.
4. To offer suggestion for reducing stress among the female staff.

HYPOTHESIS:

There is no relationship between workload and stress level.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY/SAMPLING DESIGN:

At present there are all 34 (public and private) colleges in and around villupuram district. A well designed questionnaire has been administered by the researcher himself for the above mentioned colleges. This study involves collection of primary and secondary data. The questionnaire contained three major segments. The first segment consists of general profile. The second segment consists of perception about their work and stress, its impact on family life and its impact on physical, psychological and behavioural impact. The third segment consists of suggestion to reduce and manage stress in personal and organizational view. Random samples of 110 have taken from faculty members of various departments.

TOOLS OF STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Some of the statistical tools used for the analysis of the data were percentage method and chi-square test. For all the percentage method is used to know the percentage proportion of the variables. Chi-square test is used test whether workload and stress. Anova test or F-test is used to test whether mean of two variables skill and experience are significant, does it make any difference.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

"Staff stress is a critical problem for human service professions.(Shinn, Rosario, Morch and Chestnut,1994)teaching is one of the most stressful professions, with a great degree of job stress. Job stress is a psychological syndrome in response to chronic exposure to emotional and interpersonal stressors on the job.(Maslach, schaufeli and leitur 2011).

National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health(NIOSH)estimates that more than 9000 staff members and other teaching professionals are injured or verbally or physically affected on the job everyday, Shirley cayton. Feelings of stress develop from various events, such as work overload, criticism, negligent co-workers, unco-operative peers, lack of support from their head.(Motowidlo, Manning and Packard,1996).

ANALYSIS RESULTS:

Causes of stress:

I.(Physiological, psychological and behavioural)from the listed factors causing stress at work the respondent says less staff causes stress is 14.4% shift working is 12.58%,problem with co workers is 11% majorly as highest to the total percentage.

Other factors also causing stress with lesser difference of the factor causing maximum stress. i.e. lack of facilities and lack of reward, inferior quality instruments, non availability of advanced technology is 25%,lack of cooperation is 9%,improper instruction, time pressure and managing emotions of superiors, management and their family members is around 10%.

EFFECTS OF STRESS:

The effect and symptoms of stress will be realized more when the respondent is depressed it is 69%,sleeping disorder is 65%,digestive system disorder is 26.36%,increase in blood pressure is 21.81% and anxiety is 24.54% are the major effects

Effect of socio-economic(family)life due to work stress 64% of the total respondent says that work stress have impact on family life due to shift basis, full time ,spend less time with family members, working even on government holidays, travelling long distance, no time to look after the children's and elders at home etc.

OVERALL STRESS EFFECT:

On the whole the survey reveals that maximum effect of stress is on the psychological aspect is 65%,physiological is the next about 22.72% and lastly behavioural aspect is 13%.So from this survey it understood that the effect of stress is maximum on psychology(Mental state).Rather than physical.

SKILL IS SAME FOR DIFFERENT EXPERIENCED STAFF

Skills / Exp.yrs	High efficiency	Good	Better	Poor	Total
<1	1	4	0	0	5
Above 1-3	10	34	15	0	59
Above 3-5	1	29	6	0	36
More 5	2	8	0	0	10
Total	14	75	21	0	110

*Use coding method subtracting 20 for the given data

Correction factor =(Total)²/Total no. of rows and column

=(-210)²/16=2756.25

Degree of freedom=(No. of columns-1)=3 Degree of freedom=(No. of rows-1)=3

Residual or error sum of square=Total sum of squares-(sum of squares between columns + sum of squares between rows)=409.23

ANOVA TABLE

	Sum of squares	DF	Mean square	F
Between columns	809.25	3	MSC=269.75	MSC/MSE=5.93
Between rows	469.25	3	MSR=156.41	MSR/MSE=3.43
Residual or Error	409.25	9	MSE=45.47	
Total sum of squares	1687.75	15		

The table value of F for(3,9)at 5%level of significance is 3.86,the calculated values of F for skills is 5.93 greater than the table value, hence there is significant difference between skills. The table value of F for (3,9)at 5% level of significance is 3.86,the calculated values of F for experience is 3.43 less than the table value, Hence experience does not make significant difference. Because there are human capacity, knowledge, standard(Expectation to perform),environment, motivation, interpersonal skills, educational level and etc., which determines skills level of an individual.

Hypothesis: There is no relationship between work load and stress

Factors	Yes	No	Total
Work load	57	53	110
Stress	81	29	110
Total	138	82	220

Null Hypothesis (Ho):There is no significant relationship between workload and stress.

Alternate Hypothesis(H1):There is significant relationship between work load and stress

O	E	(O-E)*2	(O-E)*2/E
81	69	144	2.086957
57	69	144	2.086957
29	41	144	3.512195
53	41	144	3.512195
			11.1983

$$\chi^2 = \frac{\sum(O-E)^2}{E} = 11.1983$$

Degree of Freedom $= (r-1)(c-1) = (2-1)(2-1) = 1$, 5% level of significant at 1 degree of freedom $= 3.841$, the calculated value of χ^2 is greater than the table value. Hence Null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore there is a relationship between workload and stress.

FINDINGS

a) The survey of female faculty regarding their work stress reveals that less staff, shift work, lack of co-operation, lack of facilities, amenities, lack of advanced technology are the major (psychological, physiological and behavioral) causes of stress.

b) More stress brings out the depression, sleeping disorder, digestive system disorder, anger, and blood pressure, anxiety as a major and maximum effect.

c) Socio-economic life is affected in great extent. More stress effect is only on the psychological state of respondent.

d) There is a relationship between the work load and stress.

SUGESSTIONS

Sl.No	Organization measure to reduce stress at work	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Awards for efficient service	50	45.45
2	Salary hike & other rewards	39	35.45
3	Proper supply of aids and amenities	48	43.63
4	Appointing more staffs	69	62.72
5	Providing quarters, schools etc.	78	70.90
6	Work pressure for providing better results	50	45

In order to give happy family and stress free life for female staff working in colleges ,the management and government should provide quarters for stay near colleges to avoid travelling long distance, schools for children in the nearby premises so that faculty can look after their children, colleges providing facilities exclusively for staff gives a sense of belongingness.

To reduce the stress due to workand work load, the administration have a procedure for purchasing instruments for every departments, necessary documents have been maintained and handed over to the staff in charge of the concern department for which the purchase is made, fill up the vacancy position by appointing right number of staff, encourage by giving awards for efficient service, faculty should working with service mind.

In order to render efficient service and to have stress free mind in general, the faculty should identify the source that cause stress in the domestic life and remove it if possible or control the situation or take it in positive sense. It is suggested to faculty, it's always better to keep elders, children's to take care of family in their absence, making interactions with family members and friends, sharing the moments of happiness and sorrows, make time for vacations, plan and prioritize the work and doing it at the right time, having good sleep for 6 to 8 hours, practicing relaxation methods like deep breathing, meditation, yoga, exercise and having a balanced diet and setting realistic goals in order to avoid stress in domestic life.

CONCLUSION

Health is just free from the disease to realize one's potential. This stress which is unavoidable has become an inherent part of life. The study was made on women staffs who are paid by the government, where to work with all their effort, will have much stress, the study was also made on the fresh staff also. This study reveals that women staff has come to this profession in order to provide service to the needy one and felt this as a respectable blessed profession prominently. Sometimes go dissatisfied as they have limited co-operation, decision making on their own, short of staff to cover etc., and many other reasons on the management part to provide as well family obligations and support from their side. This stressful state is responsible by both the staff members and administration, so the management have to take measures suggested to provide stress free environment also individual has to take effort to free themselves by balancing the work life, changing perception of stress, doing work with service mind, building good relationship with their colleague, work with smiling face and has to practice relaxation methods etc.,

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